

General-Purpose Sensing for Smart Environments: the Smart Museum use case

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Abstract—A comprehensive monitoring of the indoor environment opens the door to multiple and orthogonal application scenarios. In the context of a Smart Museum, for example, General-Purpose Sensing approaches with measurements like air quality, temperature, humidity allow estimating both user-centric metrics like visitors' comfort but, also, artifact-centric ones such as artwork preservation. Hence, in this paper, we present a CNN-LSTM (Convolutional Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory) predictive approach to forecast indoor temperature variations within Smart Museum, enabling proactive microclimate management and the prevention of potential damage to artifacts. The results show that the predictive model achieves good accuracy in temperature forecasting, with a Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) of 2% in the calculation of the Predicted Risk of Damage (PRD). This data-driven approach offers the potential to prevent damage to artifacts through proactive management of environmental conditions while simultaneously ensuring direct artifact supervision and the full exploitation of already deployed hardware.

Index Terms—IoT, Smart Museum, Smart Environment, Indoor Monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

General-Purpose Sensing refers to the practice of using sensors and hardware, initially designed for specific tasks, and exploiting them (with the data they collect) for different, often unforeseen, purposes [1]. The central concept is to utilize existing infrastructure and devices to unlock new

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applications by analyzing and interpreting data from general-purpose sensors through algorithms or AI models. Therefore, the flexibility, versatility, and cost-effectiveness of General-Purpose Sensing make it increasingly relevant in the IoT (Internet of Things) ecosystems, where heterogeneous data sources need to be dynamically interconnected or integrated without the need for (purchasing, installing, and deploying) new or specialized sensors for each use case [2], [3].

A. Background

For example, consider an increasingly popular application scenario such as the Smart Museum. There, general purpose devices such as cameras, presence, temperature, humidity, or pollutant sensors can be exploited for a variety of tasks, from security purposes to environmental monitoring, in order to achieve different goals such as maximizing visitors' comfort or preserving artifacts [4]. In fact, control of microclimatic variables is key to ensuring human health [5], [6] as well as to

preserving and preventing artifacts degradation [7]. By focusing on this second perspective, artifacts are susceptible to physico-chemical alteration processes, cumulative and irreversible in nature, which are induced by various factors acting at a microscopic level and altering the surrounding microclimate [8]. In detail, chemical deterioration is caused by interactions with atmospheric pollutants such as sulfur dioxide (SO₂), ozone (O₃), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter (PM), and volatile organic compounds (TVOC). Physical damage, instead, results from significant fluctuations in temperature and/or relative humidity, leading to repeated expansion and contraction cycles in the constituent materials. In this context, a key index that accounts for the

specific thresholds established in the regulations and also for the variations of the indoor microclimate is the Predicted Risk of Damage (PRD) [9]. This index is defined as the probability of damage that microclimatic conditions may cause to specific materials in an indoor environment. It is empirically determined based on the definition of PMV [10], according to the following eq.1:

$$PRD = (1 - 0.95e^{(-aHMR^4 - bHMR^2)}) \quad (1)$$

The PRD depends on the parameters a and b , which vary based on the considered material. These parameters are empirically determined following the standards [11] and [12] and their values for the materials considered in this study can be checked in Tab.3 in [9]. The HMR refers to the Heritage Microclimate Risk index [9], defined as follows in eq.2:

$$HMR = \frac{HMR_{env} + HMR_{osc}}{2}, \quad (2)$$

where HMR_{env} represents the risk associated with environmental parameters (i.e., temperature or humidity), while HMR_{osc} refers to the risk linked to daily fluctuations of the same parameters. According to [9], the HMR can be calculated for both humidity and temperature in accordance with threshold values and maximum fluctuations defined by the standard [12]. Here, we calculate the HMR and, consequently, the PRD only for the temperature using a two-day time moving window. This interval represents the minimum temporal limit for computing HMR_{osc} , as defined in [9], and is determined based on the hourly average temperature. This approach enables the assessment of daily damage risk associated with the PRD. Namely, the PRD is computed by incorporating feedback from the previous day's data, enabling a daily cumulative assessment of the damage risk day by day. HMR values range between -1 and 1 and are correlated with risk levels, ranging from Maximum (-1 and +1) to Minimum (0) (see Tab.1 in [9]). Based on these values, the PRD percentage thresholds can be defined, assigning a risk level within the range of 0% to 100% as reported in Table I. These thresholds depend on the material under consideration and, consequently, on the parameters a and b [9].

TABLE I
PRD THRESHOLD

Levels	Inorganic (%)	Organic (%)	Mixed (%)	Painting (%)
Maximum	100 - 87	100 - 95	100 - 97	100 - 98
High	87 - 63	95 - 77	97 - 77	98 - 88
Medium	63 - 35	77 - 48	77 - 57	88 - 64
Moderate	35 - 15	48 - 23	57 - 29	64 - 34
Low	15 - 7	23 - 9	29 - 10	34 - 12
Minimum	7 - 0	9 - 0	10 - 0	12 - 0

B. Motivations and Contribution

Traditional control systems in museums demonstrate severe limitations, while automated systems provided with IoT and AI technologies allow for proactive management of indoor microclimatic conditions, helping curators maintain optimal air quality and preventing shifts in environmental conditions that could affect both visitors' comfort and artifacts preservation [13]–[15]. In particular, temperature forecasting proves to be crucial in defining the predicted PRD, enabling the implementation of targeted risk mitigation strategies. Therefore, in this paper, we present an automated ambient control alert system to assist Smart Museum's curators in decision-making based on the analyzed alerts. Utilizing general purpose sensors already deployed for both environmental conditions and occupancy monitoring, the system continuously monitors and predicts the PDR: in particular, a CNN-LSTM (Convolutional Neural Network, Long Short-Term Memory) predictive approach is implemented to forecast indoor temperature variations within Smart Museum, thus enabling proactive microclimate management and the prevention of potential damage to artifacts.

The paper is organized as follows. Section II presents the proposed system and predictive modeling approach. In Section III, we discuss the results from the Deep Learning models and the predicted PRD. Section IV presents a few related works, while Conclusions and future work are finally discussed in Section V.

II. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. Deep learning approach

In order to enhance environmental monitoring, this work integrates a hybrid deep learning approach based on CNNs LSTM networks. This strategy enables accurate forecasting of indoor temperature variations by leveraging the most recent measurements to predict the next 24 hours. The input variables include CO₂, TVOC, humidity and temperature, along with their respective time-lagged values to capture temporal dependencies. Additionally, three new variables accounting for temporal patterns are incorporated: sinusoidal and cosinusoidal hourly projections, and the day of the week. The CNN component of the network captures short-term patterns in the data, while the LSTM component models long-term dependencies, favoring reliable predictions. However, it is important to note that, the development and implementation of this model depends heavily on a data pre-processing pipeline, which involves the identification and removal of outliers, the imputation of missing data.

1) *Pre-processing*: The dataset under consideration is constituted of 187,413 samples collected at five-minute intervals. The identification of outliers is conducted utilising the Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (DBSCAN) method. This approach is deemed appropriate due to the non-linear physical interactions characterizing the environmental variables under investigation. These interactions exhibit a high degree of complexity, whereby

variations in one variable can significantly influence the behaviour of others in non-trivial ways [16]. The process of standardization is necessary for identifying outliers in the dataset, with the aim of harmonizing the discrepancies in the units of measurement of the variables. This is due to disparities in the units of measurement that would otherwise disproportionately affect the performance of the DBSCAN method. Various DBSCAN parameters configurations have been examined, by varying the proximity radius (ϵ) in the range [0.1-1] and the minimum number of points for the cluster (Min-pts) in the range [15-50]. The optimal configuration, with $\epsilon = 0.4$ and Min-pts = 20, leads to the identification of 0.74% of the data as outliers.

The identified outliers have been replaced with missing values, that add to the ones already in the dataset. For the processing of NaN values, the time interval of the missing data has been considered. For temporal lags within the range of 20-30 units, imputation is conducted using multiple linear regression. For longer temporal lags, missing data are replaced with values from the previous week. This approach allows for a representation as realistic as possible of data fluctuations, ensuring temporal consistency and reflecting the historical behavior of the dataset in a plausible manner. While this method is relatively straightforward and empirical, the imputation of values based on historical data from the preceding week has shown to mitigate the risk of over- or under-estimation, which may be introduced by conventional predictive models lacking sufficient variability. Finally, the dataset is resampled hourly.

2) *Model architecture*: Dataset preparation for supervised learning begins with standardization. Data is structured into a 3D tensor [samples, time-steps, features], where each sample represents a time sequence, where the number of time-steps indicates previous observations used to predict the next 24 hours. The dataset is split into train and test sets, with the last two weeks reserved for testing. The optimal model is chosen based on the optimization of the hyperparameters in a grid search process involving the different parameters of the CNN, LSTM and Dropout layers. A MaxPooling1D layer follows Conv1D to reduce sequence length but is omitted if the time-step is less than or equal to 3. ReLU and Tanh activation functions are used, along with EarlyStopping (patience = 6) and the Adam optimizer with a variable learning rate (0.001, 0.01, 0.1). 20% of the train set is reserved for validation to monitor MAE and prevent overfitting. The hybrid CNN-LSTM architecture leverages CNNs for local feature extraction and LSTMs for long-term temporal dependencies, crucial for forecasting. Dropout (20%) after CNN and LSTM mitigates overfitting. Numerous studies [17], [18] have shown that this hybrid approach shows improvements in performance compared to using CNN or LSTM separately.

B. System Development

The proposed Smart Museum leverages a hybrid edge-cloud architecture [19]. General-purpose sensors (e.g., CO₂,

TVOC, humidity, temperature, light intensity, and occupancy) continuously monitor environmental parameters required for calculating various KPIs, including the PDR. We used Milesight AM-107, an advanced environmental monitoring multi-sensor device for temperature sensing used for PDR calculation ($\pm 0.3^\circ\text{C}$ in the range 0° 70°C). These sensor readings are transmitted to a central edge gateway via a long-range communication protocol, ensuring reliable and error-free data collection. At the edge level, raw data is pre-processed and preliminary KPIs are computed. The processed data is then forwarded to a cloud server, where it is stored for advanced analysis and comprehensive KPIs computation. Overall, the Smart Museum (with its distributed sensors collectively monitoring environmental conditions for artifact preservation) represents a distributed collective intelligent system because it enables decentralized decision-making, collaborative data processing, and adaptive learning.

Fig. 1. PRDs dashboard in Grafana. Historical PRDs represented with a histogram (up) and Gauge Plot (bottom) of daily risk levels for actual (left) and predicted (right) for the four materials considered separately.

Real and predicted PRD are shown in Fig.1. The temperature sensor continuously streams data to InfluxDB, a time-series database optimized for high-performance storage and retrieval. Within InfluxDB, a task is defined that monitors

the incoming sensor readings in real-time, triggering an automated email notification to the curator if any recorded value exceeds a configured threshold. Additionally, the system supports mobile app-based alerts, providing an alternative and immediate notification channel for critical environmental changes.

III. RESULTS

In this Section, the results obtained from the model training phase and the PRD calculation are discussed. The PRD calculation is determined considering both actual and predicted temperature values.

Through the implemented grid search, it is possible to evaluate the best model by applying it to the test set and comparing the predictions with the actual values. The performance of the model is evaluated by means of analysis of metrics, such as root mean squared error (RMSE), the normalized RMSE (NRMSE), the mean absolute error (MAE), and the mean absolute percentage error (MAPE), which are listed below:

$$\begin{cases} RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2} \\ MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i| \\ MAPE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \left| \frac{y_i - \hat{y}_i}{y_i} \right| \\ NRMSE = \frac{RMSE}{y_{max} - y_{min}} \end{cases}$$

where n is the length of dataset, y_i is real variable and \hat{y}_i is the predicted variable. y_{max} and y_{min} are the maximum and minimum variable in the dataset.

The configuration of the model with the best performance is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Best model architecture for temperature.

Table II reports the results of the model configuration described in Fig.2 on the test set. The model achieves

optimal results according to all metrics, as can be seen, for example, on MAPE and NRMSE, where the prediction error on the test set is at or below 4%.

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF CNN-LSTM MODEL

Metric	Value
MAE	0.654
RMSE	0.885
MAPE	0.023
NRMSE	0.041

These comprehensive metrics suggest a good model performance, with limited deviations and good predictive ability, as also shown in Fig.3, where we show the real temperature values (blue line) and the predicted temperature (dashed red line) referred to the test set.

Fig. 3. Predicted Temperature vs Real Temperature

It is now possible to calculate and compare daily PRD values considering the temperatures that have been measured and those that have been predicted for the following day (see Fig. 4). This figure shows the calculated PRD values for four types of materials: Inorganic, Organic, Mixed, and Paintings. In Table III are reported the performance metrics (MAE, RMSE, MAPE, and NRMSE) calculated for the PRDs.

Initially, we note that the MAPEs were found to be 2.7%, 2.7%, 2.7%, 2.6%, respectively, for Inorganic, Organic, Mixed, and Painting, indicating that, on average, the discrepancy between the predicted and actual values is contained within a relatively small percentage. As illustrated in Table I, this percentage of error is small compared with the risk levels previously delineated. That is to say, the range of variation between the maximum and minimum risk levels is 10% to 20%, and the error on the prediction of the PRD

TABLE III
PERFORMANCE METRICS OF PRD

Materials	MAE	RMSE	MAPE	NRMSE
Inorganic	0.666	1.000	0.027	0.011
Organic	0.718	1.312	0.027	0.014
Mixed	0.788	1.495	0.027	0.015
Paintings	0.848	1.632	0.026	0.017

is contained within these limits, for all the material under consideration. Therefore, we can safely assume that the PRD calculated on the predicted temperature is reliable and can be used for decision-making processes.

Also, from Fig.4 it is evident that the PRD has extreme values, close to 100%, indicating maximum risk of deterioration. This phenomenon can be attributed to two primary factors. Firstly, elevated temperature values have been recorded in the range, and secondly, the constant differential increase of 3-4 °C, in the range under consideration, is followed by a subsequent partial differential decrease. When constant and large differential increases are measured in the daily sub-range, followed by partial decreases, the variations are more regular, with a relatively high PRD. However, when values show more frequent but smaller fluctuations, the variability distributed over time acts as a mitigating factor, reducing the PRD. In other words, the increase in local fluctuations, although small in magnitude, tends to even out the behaviour of the dataset, lowering the PRD. In this context, therefore, fluctuations are a significant factor in risk mitigation.

IV. RELATED WORK

Several research studies exploit IoT and AI technologies for the artifact conservation monitoring.

Some of them consider the analysis of microclimatic variables to quantify the risk of deterioration [20], in few cases also associated with PRD [21], or they study predictive control of indoor microclimatic conditions [22] and alternative approaches for environmental monitoring [23]: however, to the best of our knowledge, none of them deals with the daily prediction of PRD associated with microclimatic variables through predictive analysis. Conversely, a separate research direction focus on indices related to chemical risk, such as the Lifetime Multiplier [24], or the Sedlbauer's Isopleth System [25] for mold risk evaluation, but such a thread is out of the scope of our paper. Finally, to further differentiate the presented system from existing solutions in the literature, it is hardware-agnostic (i.e., it relies totally on the sensors that are widely used in every smart museum, avoiding dependency on specialized hardware) and purposely engineered by considering robustness (the preprocessing pipeline automatically adjusts to new data distributions, ensuring robustness against intermittent failures) and adaptivity (the PRD metric is calculated relative to user-defined thresholds,

Fig. 4. Daily PRD for four materials (Inorganic, Organic, Mixed, Painting), Real and Predicted. Dashed red lines represents the limits range risk levels as reported in Tab.I.

allowing curators to customize risk thresholds without model retraining) as primary requirements.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

An integral aspect of museum management involves monitoring the risk of damage and ensuring effective prevention measures for artifact conservation. This can be achieved through comprehensive control and mitigation strategies focused on microclimatic variables. The assessment of the risk of degradation, however, requires a systematic and automatic analysis, taking into account both the measured

values and their variations, and the thresholds set by the relevant regulations.

Therefore, in the context of a Smart Museum and according to the General-Purpose Sensing approach, this paper discussed a CNN-LSTM model demonstrating strong predictive capabilities in estimating the PDR. The ability of the CNN to capture local patterns and of the LSTM to model long-term dependencies has allowed the development of a model capable of predicting temperature with an error of approximately 2% in terms of MAPE, thus allowing curators to act in a timely manner to ensure the optimal conservation of artworks. This performance is particularly relevant and this data driven approach, with its contained margin of error, offers the potential to prevent damage to artifacts through proactive management of environmental conditions, while simultaneously ensuring direct supervision of various materials. However, it is important to note that the absolute daily PRD values can be high on certain days due to hourly temperature fluctuations, which in some cases may exceed 3°C. These fluctuations are also influenced by the variability of human activity, which varies throughout the week and directly impacts the microclimate. In addition to hourly fluctuations, the absolute measured temperatures must always remain within the limits defined by the relevant regulations to ensure proper and safe management of the museum environment. The proposed CNN-LSTM model is scalable in every kind of museum scenario and adaptable to varying sensor configurations.

Future research will exactly focus on training the model with new data collected from the sensors, allowing for further optimization of the parameters in order to reduce prediction errors, and integrate new indicators that more accurately account for risk prevention and artifact preservation. Moreover, future work will include the development of a dedicated humidity prediction model, as PRD can also be quantified by considering humidity as the target variable. This would further enhance the monitoring system's capacity for effective risk mitigation and artifact preservation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Roberto Vezzani, Martino Lombardi, Augusto Pieracci, Paolo Santinelli, and Rita Cucchiara. A general-purpose sensing floor architecture for human-environment interaction. *ACM Transactions on Interactive Intelligent Systems (THIS)*, 5(2):1–26, 2015.
- [2] Claudio Savaglio, Vincenzo Barbuto, Faraz Malik Awan, Roberto Minerva, Noel Crespi, and Giancarlo Fortino. Opportunistic digital twin: an edge intelligence enabler for smart city. *ACM Transactions on Sensor Networks*.
- [3] Md Mustakin Alam, Tanjim Ahmed, Meraz Hossain, Mehedi Hasan Emo, Md Kausar Islam Bidhan, Md Tanzim Reza, Md Golam Rabiul Alam, Mohammad Mehedi Hassan, Francesco Pupo, and Giancarlo Fortino. Federated ensemble-learning for transport mode detection in vehicular edge network. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 149:89–104, 2023.
- [4] Irfanullah Khan, Antonio Guerrieri, Franco Cicirelli, A. Stephen McGough, and Giandomenico Spezzano. Human-centric based energy and comfort optimization in cognitive buildings: A review. In *2024 IEEE Conference on Pervasive and Intelligent Computing (PICom)*, pages 98–104, 2024.
- [5] Rafiq Ul Islam, Pasquale Mazzei, and Claudio Savaglio. Healthiness and safety of smart environments through edge intelligence and internet of things technologies. *Future Internet*, 16(10):373, 2024.
- [6] Luigi Scarcello, Franco Cicirelli, Antonio Guerrieri, Carlo Mastrianni, Giandomenico Spezzano, and Andrea Vinci. Pursuing energy saving and thermal comfort with a human-driven drl approach. *IEEE Transactions on Human-Machine Systems*, 53(4):707–719, 2022.
- [7] Oscar Chiantore and Tommaso Poli. Indoor air quality in museum display cases: volatile emissions, materials contributions, impacts. *Atmosphere*, 12(3):364, 2021.
- [8] Laura CIRRINCIONE, Maria La Gennusa, Giorgia Peri, Gianfranco Rizzo, and Gianluca Scaccianoce. Indoor parameters of museum buildings for guaranteeing artworks preservation and people's comfort: Compatibilities, constraints, and suggestions. *Energies*, 17(8), 2024.
- [9] Kristian Fabbri and Anna Bonora. Two new indices for preventive conservation of the cultural heritage: Predicted risk of damage and heritage microclimate risk. *Journal of Cultural Heritage*, 47:208–217, 2021.
- [10] Maher Hamdi, Gerard Lachiver, and François Michaud. A new predictive thermal sensation index of human response. *Energy and Buildings*, 29(2):167–178, 1999.
- [11] *EN 15757 Standard; Conservation of Cultural Heritage—Specifications for Temperature and Relative Humidity to Limit Climate-Induced Mechanical Damage*. European Committee for Standardization (CEN), Brussels, Belgium, 2010.
- [12] *UNI 10829; Beni di Interesse Storico e Artistico—Condizioni Ambientali di Conservazione—Misurazione ed Analisi*. UNI, Milano, Italy, 1999.
- [13] Yann Lecun and Y. Bengio. Convolutional networks for images, speech, and time-series. 01 1995.
- [14] Sepp Hochreiter and Jürgen Schmidhuber. Long short-term memory. *Neural Computation*, 9:1735–1780, 11 1997.
- [15] Guoqiang Zhang, B. Eddy Patuwo, and Michael Y. Hu. Forecasting with artificial neural networks:: The state of the art. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 14(1):35–62, 1998.
- [16] Shan Zhou, Hong Liu, Yong Ding, and Yuxin Wu. The effects of temperature and humidity on the voc emission rate from dry building materials. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 609(4):042001, sep 2019.
- [17] Xingjian Shi, Zhourong Chen, Hao Wang, Dit-Yan Yeung, Wai-kin Wong, and Wang-chun Woo. Convolutional lstm network: a machine learning approach for precipitation nowcasting. In *Proceedings of the 29th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems - Volume 1, NIPS'15*, page 802–810, Cambridge, MA, USA, 2015. MIT Press.
- [18] Zhipeng Shen, Yuanming Zhang, Jiawei Lu, Jun Xu, and Gang Xiao. A novel time series forecasting model with deep learning. *Neurocomputing*, 396, 04 2019.
- [19] Rafiq Ul Islam, Mariangela Viviani, Simone Colace, Sara Laurita, Claudio Savaglio, and Giancarlo Fortino. Improving visitors experience in smart museums. In *Proceedings of The First Latin American Conference on Internet of Things*. IEEE, April 2025. To appear.
- [20] Alessandro Bile, Hamed Tari, Andreas Grinde, Francesca Frasca, Anna Maria Siani, and Eugenio Fazio. Novel model based on artificial neural networks to predict short-term temperature evolution in museum environment. *Sensors*, 22(2):615, 2022.
- [21] Efstathia Tringa and Konstantia Tolika. Analysis of the outdoor microclimate and the effects on greek cultural heritage using the heritage microclimate risk (hmr) and predicted risk of damage (prd) indices: Present and future simulations. *Atmosphere*, 14(4), 2023.
- [22] Glykeria Loupa, Georgios Dabanlis, Georgia Resta, Evangelia Kostenidou, and Spyridon Rapsomanikis. Indoor microclimatic conditions and air pollutant concentrations in the archaeological museum of abdera, greece. *Aerobiology*, 2(2):29–43, 2024.
- [23] Mauro Bacci, Costanza Cucci, Andrea Mencaglia, and A.G. Mignani. Innovative sensors for environmental monitoring in museums. *Sensors*, 8, 03 2008.
- [24] Harold Enrique Huerto-Cardenas, Niccolò Aste, Claudio Del Pero, Stefano Della Torre, and Fabrizio Leonforte. Effects of climate change on the future of heritage buildings: Case study and applied methodology. *Climate*, 2021.
- [25] Klaus Sedlbauer. Prediction of mould fungus formation on the surface of and inside building components. 01 2001.